

Example Data Management Plan – complete version with full responses

ZEB34A A phase II Clinical trial of an investigational medicinal product Data Management Plan

Data Stewardship Wizard (DSW) Example Data Management Plan

Complete version with full responses

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ELIXIR-UK

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Based on

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(Q1) Proposal name

ZEB34A – A randomised, open-label, multicentre, phase II clinical trial to compare Zebaxinate to standard of care therapy for breast cancer patients.

(Q2) Description of the data: Type of study

This study is a phase II clinical trial of an investigational medicinal product (CTIMP) and aims to establish the safety profile of the addition of ZEB34A medication to standard care for breast cancer patients.

(Q3) Description of the data: Types of data

This CTIMP involves the capture of electronic healthcare data at the site by research nurses. This data will be stored on electronic Case Report Forms (eCRFs) including data such as blood results, demographics, pharmacovigilance data, treatment records and quality of life assessments. Data is pseudonymised, and only data of birth and patient initials are captured at the trial site, together with a Clinical Trials Unit-generated trial number.

No qualitative data will be collected as part of this trial.

(Q4) Description of the data: Origin of the data

Data in this project comes from a single source – the ZEB34A clinical trial, hosted by the University. This trial is a randomised, open label, multi-centre, phase II clinical trial hosted at sites throughout the UK. The clinical trial data is generated as new primary data collected by research nurses at approved clinical trial sites hosted at NHS hospitals.

Trial sites will determine whether they utilise paper or electronic Case Report Forms (CRFs) for their preferred mode of Data will be captured at source on electronic CRFs

(Q5) Description of the data: Format and scale of the data

Data from this project will be derived from the following:

CRFs collecting data from visits over a six-month period for patients on the trial (n=150). Timepoints include Baseline and eligibility assessments, treatment, one-month, three-month six month follow up, Serious Adverse Event form plus validated quality of life questionnaire (EQ5D).

This equates to approximately 35,000 data variables over the 150 participants, or approximately 50Gb of data stored in csv files.

(Q6) Managing, storing and curating data

Data will be captured by research nurses listed on the delegation log at approved sites. Sites will enter data onto either tablets with electronic CRFs. Clinical trial visits include baseline, randomisation, treatment, one, three, and six-month follow up.

The ZEB34A clinical trial data is held within the University's Research Data Storage Service (RDSS), a standard activity for CTU. The RDSS department manage ownership and staff access to both the compute and storage systems this project will utilise. This system is resilient, secure and networked storage with on-site and cloud back-up. All data compliant with the UK GDPR and Clinical Trials Regulations and University data handling policies.

Data files will be stored within unique locations within the storage system with consistent naming strategies with access limited to the applicant and associated named members of the trial management team

(Q7) Metadata standards and data documentation

Standard metadata will be produced for this clinical trial. The metadata files uniquely identify each data object within the study CRFs and will be replicated and structured consistently across to the sub-study to enhance its discoverability and reusability.

Methodologies for statistical analyses performed will be documented thoroughly. All outputs of this project will be accompanied by appropriate documentation, code commenting and update to resources design for these purposes.

Data files will be stored within unique locations with consistent naming strategies with access limited to the applicant and associated named members of the trial management team.

The project will follow the UK Data Service guidelines for describing quantitative data.

(Q8) Data preservation strategy and standards

All data for the ZEB34A sub-study will be stored as pseudonymised datasets, and may only be accessed or shared by the Clinical Trials Unit in an anonymised format for future research, in compliance with the

initial terms of consent by the trial participants.

Essential records will be maintained in a legible condition with data files saved in open format (csv files). Archival facilities will be secure, with appropriate environmental controls and adequate protection from fire, flood and unauthorised access.

Essential documents of the sponsor/trial organisers and investigators will be retained for 15 years after completion of the trial.

In multi-site trials trial documents held by the Principal Investigator will be archived by the University as host organisation in accordance with local policy and GCP.

(Q9) Where will data be shared?

Following publication, we intend to publish the data from this sub-study to the ISRCTN Registry to ensure reusability and accessibility of these findings. All source data will be made publicly available through the UK Data Service. Methodologies including statistical analyses and scripts and results will be published in open-access scientific journals.

(Q10) When will data be available?

Data will be shared in a timely manner and shared publicly at the time of its publication, or within one year from the project end date. All source data will be made publicly available through the UK Data Service. Methodologies including statistical analyses and scripts and results will be published in open-access scientific journals.

(Q11) How will data be made findable and accessible?

The main study results will be made available to the research community with publication of the full trial methods and results through publication in peer-reviewed scientific journals presented in a way that allows inclusion in future systematic reviews and on behalf of all collaborators

The ZEB34A trial will be registered on the ISRCTN Registry citing the main ZEB34A clinical trial. ISRCTN registry attributes a unique object identification (UOI) number which may be referenced in future citations.

This non-commercial trial, will follow the CONSORT guidelines to prepare the final study report.

(Q12) How will data be made reusable?

The main study results will be made available to the research community with publication of the full

trial methods and results through publication in peer-reviewed scientific journals presented in a way that allows inclusion in future systematic reviews and on behalf of all collaborators.

Metadata will be prepared to a sufficient standard to enable users to reanalyse the data and understand its origin and use.

(Q13) Restrictions or delays to sharing, with planned actions to limit such restrictions

The primary datasets are under the Data Controllorship of the University Clinical Trials Unit, whereby the University are designated Sponsor and data controller.

Due to this project being an ongoing clinical trial, data cannot be shared until the primary analysis have been performed and main publication been made.

(Q14) Secondary use

Data controllership and the consent model this project will enable the future usage of the data generated in this trial. For all future use, including secondary analysis datasets will only be provided as fully anonymised format and following the publication of primary analyses.

(Q15) Formal information/data security standards

Data provided as part of the initial clinical trial ZEB34A was compliant with the requirements of ICH-GCP and the clinical trials regulations, following all Clinical Trials Unit policies and procedures.

Data will be stored on secure systems with access only to the project team.

(Q16) Main risks to data security

All data available to researchers on this project, whilst being derived from patients, will have undergone pseudonymisation by staff within the Clinical Trials Unit and/or National Cancer Biobank and will be released to the project after satisfying their information security and governance procedures.

Participants of the ZEB34A Trial will only be identified by their initials, date of birth and trial number. Data Scientists working on the data will not be members of staff who have access to the pseudonymisation key, and therefore will not be able to re-identify patients as per the UK Data Service End User License Agreement.

Data will be stored on compute systems which have been designed by the University's RDSS to be ISO27001 compliant and capable of holding data with a Highly Confidential classification.

(Q17) Capabilities

The University provides all projects with up to 5 terabytes of storage on the centrally managed Research Data Store Service to host data for long term storage in compliance with funding requirements and to allow public access to data where governance and researchers require. Provision of funding throughout the retention period of this data was secured through the funding application and will be ring-fenced by the University's research Data Storage Service to ensure appropriate retention of the data.

(Q18) Maintaining and implementing the Data Management Plan

This data management plan (DMP) has been produced using the BBSRC template DMP and will be reviewed annually, or in times of change, or if any issues relating to compliance are observed. It is the responsibility of members of the project management team (notably the data scientist and Senior Statistician) to maintain this DPM as a living document throughout the duration of the research project

(Q19) Environmental considerations

The University holds an up-to-date, ISO 14001 certified environmental management system, which has been held continuously since 2012. This covers good practice and continual improvement of the University's environmental aspects including energy, procurement, pollution, travel, waste, water and biodiversity

(Q20) Responsibilities

All members of the project team (including academic applicants, project partners and appointed posts) will have responsibility for project oversight, data management, metadata creation, data security and data quality assurance, and assisted by other University departments including information security and Governance.